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Agency Compensation and Financial Performance of Quoted Manufacturing Firms in Nigeria

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ABSTRACT

This study analysed the relationship between agency compensation and financial performance of quoted manufacturing firms in Nigeria. Panel data were sourced from the financial statements of the quoted manufacturing firms. Return on equity and earnings per share were modeled as the function of executive salaries, executive equity incentives, executive bonuses and ownership concentration. The study adopted panel data ordinary least square as method of data analysis. Model one found that agency compensation accounts for approximately 74% variation in return on equity of quoted consumer goods manufacturing companies in Nigeria. The magnitude is such that, a unit increase in OC and EEI will result in a 0.115 and 0.007 units fall in return on equity or vice versa, while on the other hand, a unit rise in ES and EB will lead to a 0.0.227 and 0.167 increase in the return on equity of quoted consumer firms in Nigeria. Model two found that agency compensation accounts for approximately 82% variation in earnings per share of quoted consumer goods manufacturing firms in Nigeria. The coefficient of the parameters or endogenous variables show that ownership concentration and executive equity incentives have negative relationship with earnings per share, while executive salaries and executive bonuses have positive relationship with earnings per share of quoted consumer goods manufacturing firms in Nigeria. The magnitude is such that, a unit increase in OC and EEI will result in a 0.115 and 0.007 units fall in earnings per share or vice versa, while on the other hand, a unit rise in ES and EB will lead to a 0.0.227 and 0.167 increase in the earnings per share of quoted consumer firms in Nigeria. From the findings, the study conclude that agency compensation determine the financial performance of the quoted firms. The study recommends that the manufacturing firms should consider establishment policies for executive stockholding and policy makers need to provide adequate regulation on the determination of equity incentive of the directors of listed companies.

Keywords: Agency Compensation, Financial Performance, Manufacturing Firms, Nigeria

INTRODUCTION

The core assumptions of agency theory are that managers may maximize their own utility instead of enhancing shareholder value (Jensen & Meckling, 1976; Demsetz, 1983); information is distributed asymmetrically between principals and agents; contracts are not costless when writing and enforcing (Fama & Jensen, 1983) and the parties have perfect rationality or limited (bounded) rationality. The value of firms depends on the extent of the agent's efforts and the risks available (Jahani, Zalgahdr-Nasab & Soofi, 2013). The classic principal-agent model, the divergence of managers from shareholder value maximization and pursuing their own interests at the expense of shareholders causes agency problems. Due to information asymmetry, owners have no knowledge whether managers are making the necessary efforts or the right decisions. The owners incur monitoring costs to gather information on the actions of

managers while managers incur bonding costs, by making efforts at the expense of their own utility and implementing the contractual terms in order to reduce the agency conflict (Jensen & Meckling, 1976).

Agency cost is the internal cost that firm incurred due to the conflict of interest the principal (shareholders) and the agent (management team). This implies that the shareholders pay agency costs to the managers for their managerial efficiency towards shareholders interest. Agency costs have attracted attention in finance and it is increasingly becoming more crucial in today's business due to the extending ownership separation and control responsibilities. The adverse implications of these actions are then felt in the form of the destruction of shareholder wealth and wider impacts on other corporate stakeholders, such as debt providers, employees and society in general. Jensen and Meckling (1976) opined that agency costs arise from the conflicts between principal (shareholders) and agent (managers). The firm is made to commit the agency costs in order to ensure that managers take decision in the best interest of shareholders. An increase in agency costs would result in high operating costs leading to lower operating profit that would affect the performance of the firm. On the other end, increase in the agency costs implies that the managers are motivated enough to align their interest with the interest of the shareholders which would lead to increase in financial performance. In Nigeria, agency problem has become a big problem for most firms in the country resulting in the decline performance of firms especially in the consumer goods sector of the economy. Hence, studying factors that influence the firm performance is vital and beneficial in the perception of investors and shareholders.

Firm performance determines the ability to earn profit and measures shareholders' wealth. Firm performance can be measured using productivity, profitability, growth, employment generation or customers' satisfaction but this study focused on the profitability. The evaluation of the performance of firm and its efficiency are critical determinant of the effectiveness of the managers. Managers which are vested with daily running of the firm's activities sometimes show more concern on issues that are of benefit to them at the expense of the firm and investors. The self-interest of the managers led to the agency cost being incurred by the firm. The first is the agency problem that arises when the desires or goals of the principal and agent conflict and it is difficult or expensive for the principal to verify what the agent is actually doing (Frierman and Viswanath, 2019). It describes the fundamental conflict between self-interested managers and owners, when the former have the control of the firm but the latter bears most of the wealth effects (Kaijage and Elly, 2014). The agency relationships and the conflicts lead to private benefit of control and the expropriation of the wealth of owners (Dyck & Zingales, 2004) bankruptcy or liquidation (Jensen & Meckling, 1976) which is agency costs. The agency cost is detrimental to the investors and to the corporation as a whole. Agency cost and financial performance of quoted firms in Nigeria.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Agency Cost

Jensen and Mecklings (1976) defined agency costs in light of the firm as a nexus of relationship. In the definition, they concentrated largely on the possible costs, which might arise when a firm (the principal) hires managers from outside (the agent) to act on its behalf. Along that framework, they developed agency theory within the context of the conflicts of interest between corporate managers and equity and debt holders who are seldom if ever involved in the day-to-day running of the business. In their own words, agency cost of a firm is the sum of: (1) the monitoring expenditure by the principal, (2) the bonding expenditures by the agent, (3) the residual loss. The definition is explicit about the key sources of agency related costs to a firm (monitoring, bonding and residual loss). The reduced welfare of the principal is the residual loss.

The seminal work of Jensen and Mecklings (1976) elaborated that this residual loss mostly comes about due to the imperfection of 'the agency arrangements and agreements. Monitoring of an agent certainly brings about a reduced (not eliminates) agency cost from a given angle (but also brings about another form of agency cost- the monitoring cost, in addition to the residual loss). The leftover extent, which may not be covered by monitoring and bonding, is the residual loss. The perquisite consumption using free cash flow, the empire building, as well as the shrinking behaviour of the manager, all brings about

reduced welfare of the principal (the firm), which is regarded as residual loss, inasmuch as they cannot be prevented by simple monitoring or bonding agreements, and they are borne by the residual owners of the business. Agency cost may be measured using different approaches such as: total asset turnover (Singhand Davidson, 2003); operating expense to sales ratio (Wang, 2010), administrative expense to sales ratio (Ang, Cole & Lin, 2000) earnings volatility, advertising and research and development expense to sales ratio and floatation cost (Crutchley& Hansen, 1989).

Asset turnover is viewed as a measure of assets efficiency/utilization. The measure reflects the efficiency with which assets are applied in the generation of revenue (Ellis, 1998). On the other hand, asset dis-utilization as indicator of losses in revenue in relation to the investment in the assets is an indicator of the inefficiency in assets use. Of the three manifestations of managers' selfish pursuits, the pursuit of empire building and shrinking behaviour could be best captured by how well the manager utilizes the firm's assets in generating revenue for the firm. In pursuing empire building, the firm's hard-earned cash has to be channeled to any available investment opportunity, without a dime being spared, even where no positive present value investment is available. This could be best gauged by the inverse proxy of asset utilization. In the same vein, shrinking behaviour which is normally pursued in order to avoid being a takeover prey may require the manager to avoid as much as possible, pursuing the desired activities that may bring about financial growth to the firm. As such, assets (such as cash) will be lying idle, while profitable investments are out there for the take. Thus, here also, the inverse proxy of asset utilization will be most handy to capture this tendency.

Agency theory has brought forward the concept of agency conflict and the cost that arises out of it (Jensen & Meckling, 1976). Agency costs are one of the internal costs attached with the agents that occur due to the misalignment of the interest between the agent and principal. It embraces the cost of examining and picking up a suitable agent, collecting of information to fix performance benchmarks, watching to control the agent's action, bonding costs and the loss due to the inefficient decisions of the agents. Jensen and Meckling (1976) described the agency cost as the aggregate of the monitoring cost, bonding cost and residual loss. The consequences of the agent's shirking of his responsibilities or deviance from his duty to act in the interest of the company are known as agency costs. Agency costs refer to the decline in the firm's value due to agent's behaviour, which are in divergence with the owner's interests (Fleming, 2015). Upon detection of the possibility of this divergence of interests, it is natural for the principal to put in place a mechanism for monitoring the acts of the agent, thus incurring additional costs. They are referred to as monitoring and bonding costs.

Monitoring costs are those costs that are incurred in relation to activities like imposing budget and operating restrictions and constraints on the agent and linking agent's compensation with the outcome of monitoring. Bonding costs, on the other hand, are incurred by the agent (upon approval by the principal) on activities such as accepting contractual limitations on the agent's decision making power and agreeing to have accounts audited by a qualified auditor. The agency costs in any enterprise depend on the lack of information about the agent's activities, and the costs of monitoring and analyzing the management's performance, the costs of devising a bonus scheme which rewards the agent maximizing the principal's welfare and the costs for determining and enforcing policy rules. They further also depend on the supply of replacement managers (Fleming, 2015).

Executive Compensation

In modern firms, top executives are normally paid salary plus short-term incentives or bonuses. This combination of fixed salary and variable components like bonuses are often referred to as total cash compensation. Short-term incentives usually are formula-driven and have some performance criteria attached depending on the role of the executive. This is to motivate managers to work hard to achieve good results for the firm's owners. In many cases, top executives are known to be offered ownership stake in the business as a motivation for them. For example, the Sales manger's performance related bonus may be based on incremental revenue growth turnover; a chief executive officer's bonus may be based on incremental profitability and revenue growth. Bonuses are after-the-fact and often discretionary. Executives may also be compensated with a mixture of cash and shares of the company which is almost always subject to vesting restrictions (Edmans, Gabaix, &Jenter, 2017). Executive compensation can be

fixed or variable like salaries which are normally fixed and performance bonuses which vary based on the performance of the business. They can also be long-term such as stock options or short-term such as formula driven performance incentives like bonuses. Below, we shall discuss some of them.

Another method of dealing with agency problem is by rewarding the agent suitably for the successful pursuit of the principal's interest. The following passage aptly explains the working of this strategy. It has also been suggested that managerial ownership can align the interest between the managers and owners and therefore would reduce the agency costs of a company. It is in this light that stock options were included within the scope of executive compensation. Thus, this theory postulates that periodic performance reviews and incentives in the form of bonuses and stock options can help reduce agency costs (Fleming, 2015). This is presumably so because satisfied managers will be less likely to appropriate organizational resources for self-benefit. This theory has been the subject of much research. Jensen and Murphy (1972) suggested that while the relationship between executive compensation and creation of shareholder wealth is statistically significant, it is too weak to provide any assistance as to what constitutes a proper incentive to the chief executive officer. Wallsten in his research comes to the conclusion that executive compensation and performance are strongly linked when the firm's market value increases, but not when the market value decreases. When firms do well, top executives receive large raises that are adjusted depending on how well the firm did, but when the firm does badly, the CEO sees little compensation revision, up or down (Frierman & Viswanath, 2019).

Executive compensation which was hitherto considered a matter worth discussing in only boardrooms, annual general meetings and by academicians suddenly transformed into a matter of intense public debate and quite often, public condemnation. The collapse of major institutions like the Lehman Brothers, Merrill Lynch, Fannie Mae, Freddie Mac, Citigroup, AIG saw the markets making an epic loss even as various executives who lost their jobs walked away with huge compensation as severance packages. While the cause of the financial crisis itself was widely attributed to the recklessness of the executive management of these institutions, it was ironical that these executives were seen as the only class of people who seemed to have made wealth in the midst of all the financial mess.

Fixed Salaries

Fixed salary is the fixed amount of money or compensation paid to an employee on a regular basis in return for work performed for the employer. Salary is normally paid at fixed intervals, usually monthly. Salary is typically determined by comparing market pay rates for people performing similar work/role in similar industries in the same geographical area. Salary is also determined by leveling the pay rates and salary ranges established by an individual employer. Salary is also affected by the number of people available to perform the specific job in the employer's employment locale. Thus, the salary will be affected by market forces in an open economy. Although fixed salaries do not have much relation to management performance, most incentives are based on a fixed salary. Other elements within the compensation contract increase when salary increases. Managers that are risk averse have a relatively larger part of fixed salary as part of their total remuneration (Eric, Brisker, Don, Autore and David, 2014). The fixed salaries as explained connote a positive reinforcement by management as to the official/performance of their top management staff. This is usually a documented agreement as to the remuneration of these top management staff based on performance as predicated by merits. Higher fixed salaries are usually linked to higher proficiency, operation, efficiency, and performance directors and top management staff (Falato, 2015). The statutory restriction on managerial remuneration is a special feature of company law legislation in India and can be said to be a direct inheritance of the managing agency system. It was in accordance with the Companies and Allied Matter Act 1990 as amended introduced for the first time, the concept of an overall limit on managerial remuneration, as well as the concept of reckoning of net profits for the purpose of determining the percentage which managerial remuneration should bear to the net profits.

The Companies Act lays down the overall limits to managerial remuneration. The Act stipulates that the total managerial remuneration payable by a public company, to its directors including managing director and whole-time director and its manager in respect of any financial year shall not exceed eleven percent of the net profits of that company for that financial year. It further provides that the remuneration payable

to any one managing director or whole-time director or manager shall not exceed five percent of the net profits of the company and if there is more than one such director, the remuneration shall not exceed ten percent of the net profits to all such directors and managers taken together (Hou, 2016). Further the remuneration payable to directors, who are neither managing directors nor whole-time directors, shall not exceed one percent of the net profits of the company if there is a managing director, whole-time director or manager and the limit is fixed at three percent otherwise. The Act also provides for remuneration of directors where the company does not make any profits. In such a case, the company may provide for remuneration to directors in accordance with the provisions of Schedule V of the CAMA and if the same cannot be complied with, then with the approval of the Central Government.

Equity Incentives

Executives of corporations are responsible for corporate strategic operational, managerial, investment, financing and disbursement decisions, which ultimately impact on shareholder value. But, considering that the managers are not the only owners of the firm and their effort in most cases may be opaque in running a company, they may tend to pursue personal interests to benefit themselves and consequently undertake actions potentially not in the best interest of shareholders. Such opportunistic behavior is referred to as moral hazard and gives a rise to an agency conflicts between shareholders and a manager principal and agent conflicts (Berle and Means, 2002). In order to ensure that managers undertake actions that are in the shareholders' best interests, firm owners may either create corporate governance systems and mechanisms to perform an over sighting role or tie manager's remuneration to the performance of a company. The latter is implemented by including accounting performance metrics in the managers' bonus contracts or by compensating managers with equity instruments, the value of which depends on the company's equity price. For this reason, share-based awards accumulation, a manager's ownership in the company increases and her interests become well aligned with those of shareholders (Bettis, Bizjak & Lemmon, 2005). Executive stock holdings as explained, increases stock holders' confidence in the operation and activities of the firm. This therefore fosters the purchase of the stock of the company thereby boosting its capital base which translates to better liquidity for operation and in that manner drives up discretionary accruals, creates better real activity management and promotes turnover on firms' assets which could have been fallow in the lack of executive stock holding.

Bonuses

Based on the signaling effect as explained, bonuses to top management aids operation by relatively boosting effective and efficient response of those managers towards finding active solution to organizational problems, this incentive as backed by motivational theories promotes in-house activities which translates to better strategic inclination of the firms and is worked on by technical and operational staff. The end result of this is usually an increase in firm's annual discretionary accruals coupled with increasing asset turnover, although real activity management is usually a positive and direct function of the ability of managers to reward staff.

Agency Monitoring Cost

Monitoring cost involves the cost associated with the monitoring and assessing of the agent's performance in the firm. The various expenditures covered under the monitoring cost are the payment for watching, compensating and evaluating the agent's behaviour. Owners appoint boards to monitor the managers; hence the cost of maintaining a board is also considered as a monitoring cost. The monitoring cost also includes the recruitment and training and development expenses made for the executives. These costs are incurred by the shareholders in the initial stage but in the later stage, it is borne by the managers because they are compensated to cover these expenses (Famaand Jensen, 1983). The owners of a company can establish systems for monitoring the actions and performance of management, to try to ensure that management are acting in their best interests. An example of monitoring is the requirement for the directors to present an annual report and accounts to the shareholders, setting out the financial performance and financial position of the company. These accounts are audited, and the auditors present a report to the shareholders (Liao and Lin, 2017). Preparing accounts and having them audited has a cost.

Bonding costs

The third aspect of agency costs is costs that might be incurred to provide incentives to managers to act in the best interests of the shareholders. These are sometimes called bonding costs. These costs are intended to reduce the size of the agency problem. Directors and other senior managers might be given incentives in the form of free shares in the company, or share options. In addition, directors and senior managers might be paid cash bonuses if the company achieves certain specified financial targets (Liao and Lin, 2017). The remuneration packages for directors and senior managers are therefore an important element of agency costs.

Agency Cost of Debt

The agency costs of debt have been widely discussed, but the benefits of debt in motivating managers and their organizations to be efficient have been ignored. Managers with substantial free cash flow can increase dividends or repurchase stock and thereby pay out current cash that would otherwise be invested in low-return projects or wasted (Singh and Davidson, 2013). This leaves managers with control over the use of future free cash flows, but they can promise to pay out future cash flows by announcing a permanent increase in the dividend. Such promises are weak because dividends can be reduced in the future.

The fact that capital markets punish dividend cuts with large stock price reductions is consistent with the agency costs of free cash flow. Debt creation, without retention of the proceeds of the issue, enables managers to effectively bond their promise to pay out future cash flows. Thus, debt can be an effective substitute for dividends, something not generally recognized in the corporate finance literature (Singh and Davidson, 2013). By issuing debt in exchange for stock, managers are bonding their promise to pay out future cash flows in a way that cannot be accomplished by simple dividend increases. In doing so, they give shareholder recipients of the debt the right to take the firm into bankruptcy court if they do not maintain their promise to make the interest and principle payments. Thus debt reduces the agency costs of free cash flow by reducing the cash flow available for spending at the discretion of managers.

These control effects of debt are a potential determinant of capital structure. Issuing large amounts of debt to buy back stock also sets up the required organizational incentives to motivate managers and to help them overcome normal organizational resistance to retrenchment which the payout of free cash flow often requires (Singh and Davidson, 2013). The threat caused by failure to make debt service payments serves as an effective motivating force to make such organizations more efficient. Stock repurchases for debt or cash also has tax advantages. Interest payments are tax deductible to the corporation, and that part of the repurchase proceeds equal to the seller's tax basis in the stock is not taxed at all.

Agency Theory

An agent is a person who acts on behalf of another person, the principal, in dealing with other people. For example, a selling agent acts on behalf of a principal, a manufacturer of goods, to sell goods on the manufacturer's behalf. Similarly, a stock broker is an agent who acts on behalf of a client (the principal) to buy or sell shares on the client's behalf. The agent acts on the name of the principal, and commits the principal to agreements and transactions. In company law, the directors act as agents of the company (Ang, Cole and Lin, 2016). The board of directors as a whole, and individual directors, has the authority to bind the company to contractual agreements with other parties. Since most of the powers to act on behalf of the company are given to the board of directors, the directors (and the management of a company) have extensive powers in deciding what the company should do, what its objectives should be, what its business strategies should be, how it should invest and what its targets for performance should be.

As agents of the company, directors have a fiduciary duty to the company. A fiduciary duty is a duty of trust. A director must act on behalf of the company in total good faith, and must not put his personal interests before the interests of the company. If a director is in breach of this fiduciary duty he could be held liable in law, if the company were to take legal action against him. Legal action by a company against a director for breach of fiduciary duty would normally be taken by the rest of the board of directors or, possibly, a majority of the shareholders acting in the name of the company (Ang, Cole and Lin, 2016).

Agency theory is based on the idea that when a company is first established, its owners are usually also its managers. As a company grows, the owners appoint managers to run the company. The owners expect the managers to run the company in the best interests of the owners; therefore a form of agency relationship exists between the owners and the managers. Many firms borrow, and a significant proportion of the long-term capital of a company might come from various sources of debt capital, such as bank loans, lease finance and bond issues (debentures, loan stock and so on). Major lenders also have an interest in how the company is managed, because they want to be sure that the company will be able to repay the debt with interest (Fleming, 2015).

Agency model is considered as one of the oldest theory in the literature of the management and economics (Daily, Dalton, & Rajagopalan, 2003; Wasserman, 2006). Agency theory discusses the problems that surface in the firms due to the separation of owners and managers and emphasizes on the reduction of this problem. This theory helps in implementing the various governance mechanisms to control the agents' action in the jointly held corporations. Berle and Means (1932) found that the modern corporation of the USA was having dispersed ownership, and it leads to the separation of ownership from control. In a joint stock company, the ownership is held by individuals or groups in the form of stock and these shareholders (principals) delegates the authority to the managers (agents) to run the business on their behalf (Jensen & Meckling, 1976; Ross, 1973), but the major issue is whether these managers are performing for the owners or themselves. Adam Smith (1937) is perhaps the first author to suspect the presence of agency problem and since then it has been a motivating factor for the economists to cultivate the aspects of agency theory. Smith forecasted in his work *The Wealth of Nations* that if an organization is managed by a person or group of persons who are not the real owners, then there is a chance that they may not work for the owners' benefit.

Berle and Means (1932) later fostered this concern in their thesis, where they analyzed the ownership structure of the large firms of the USA and obtained that agents appointed by the owners control large firms and carry the business operations. They argued that the agents might use the property of the firm for their own end, which will create the conflict between the principals and agents. The financial literature in the 1960s and 1970s described the agency problem in the organizations through the problem of risk-sharing among the cooperating parties (Arrow, 1971; Wilson, 1968) involved in the organizations. There are individuals and groups in the firm having different risk tolerance and their action differs, accordingly. The principal or the owners, who invest their capital and take the risk to acquire the economic benefits, whereas the agents, who manage the firm are risk averse and concerned in maximizing their private benefits. Both the principal and agent are having opposite risk preferences and their problem in risk-sharing creates the agency conflict, which is broadly covered under the agency theory. Ross (1973) and Mitnick (1975) have shaped the theory of agency and came up with two different approaches in their respective works. Ross regarded the agency problem as the problem of incentives, while Mitnick considered the problem occurs due to the institutional structure, but the central idea behind their theories is similar.

Ross identified the principal agent problem as the consequence of the compensation decision and opined that the problem does not confine only in the firm, rather it prevails in the society as well. The institutional approach of Mitnick helped in developing the logics of the core agency theory and it was possibly designed to understand the behavior of the real world. His theory propagated that institutions are built around agency and grow to reconcile with the agency. Alchian and Demsetz (1972) and Jensen and Meckling (1976) defined a firm as a 'set of contracts between the factors of production. They described that firms are the legal fictions, where some contractual relationships exist among the persons involved in the firm. Agency relationship is also a kind of contract between the principal and agent, where both the party work for their self-interest that leads to the agency conflict. In this context, principals exercise various monitoring activities to curb the actions of the agents to control the agency cost.

In the principal-agent contract, the incentive structure, labour market and information asymmetry plays a crucial role and these elements helped in building the theory of ownership structure. Jensen and Meckling (1976) portrayed the firm as a black box, which operates to maximise its value and profitability. The

maximization of the wealth can be achieved through a proper coordination and teamwork among the parties involved in the firm. However, the interest of the parties differs, the conflict of interest arises, and it can only be relegated through managerial ownership and control. The self-interested parties also knew that their interest can only be satisfied if the firm exists. Hence, they perform well for the survival of the firm. Same way, Fama (1980) advocated that the firms can be disciplined by the competition from the other players, which monitors the performance of the entire team and the individual persons.

Empirical Review

Mohammed et al. (2022) investigated executive compensation's impact on non-financial firms' financial performance in Nigeria. They found negative effects of salary, bonuses, and stock-based compensation on return on equity, while executive pension had a positive impact. Ibeawuchi and Onuora (2021) explored the relationship between executive compensation and performance in Nigerian consumer goods companies. Their findings revealed a negative effect of CEOs' salary on performance, while board directors' cash compensation showed a positive but insignificant impact. Onuorah et al. (2019) examined the influence of compensation management on employee performance in Nigerian organizations. They found no negative significant effects of equity-based, competency-based, or performance-based compensation on employee performance.

Okeke et al. (2022) investigated compensation strategy and employee performance in Nigerian oil and gas companies. Their study revealed significant positive relationships between competency-based, job-based, and performance-based compensation, suggesting a favorable impact on employee performance. Eke et al. (2023) explored the correlation between employee welfare and the financial performance of listed manufacturing firms in Nigeria. They utilized an ex post facto research design, analyzing secondary data from annual reports of seven selected firms spanning from 2015 to 2021. The study measured employee welfare through remuneration and training, while financial performance was gauged using return on assets (ROA) and return on equity (ROE). Their findings indicated a significant positive association between employee welfare, as measured by both remuneration (ER) and training (ET), and financial performance in terms of ROA and ROE for the listed manufacturing firms in Nigeria. Based on these results, the researchers concluded that there exists a substantial relationship between employee welfare and financial performance within this context. In light of their findings, the researchers recommended that management should prioritize ongoing employee training initiatives, which can enhance employee confidence and proficiency in their roles.

Ifeanyi et al. (2020) studied the effect of compensation management on employee performance in the Manufacturing Industry. They found significant relationships between salary and benefits programs with employees' performance, recommending continued provision of security benefits to enhance overall productivity. Adeoye (2019) examined compensation management and workers' motivation in the Nigerian insurance sector. The study found a weak association between reward administration and workers' motivation, suggesting the need for periodic salary reviews to align with other sectors in Nigeria's financial industry. Onuorah et al. (2019) focused on compensation administration's effect on employee performance in Nigerian organizations. They concluded that compensation administration had a significant effect on employee performance, despite finding no negative significance effects of various compensation types. Adegrooye et al. (2017) reviewed the relationship between executive compensation and firm performance in Nigerian firms. They identified gaps in existing research, emphasizing the need for further studies to explore different types of compensation and consider market-based measures of firm performance in Nigeria.

Gap in Literature

The empirical literature on agency compensation and firm performance in Nigeria reveals several gaps that the present study aims to address. Primarily, existing studies have predominantly focused on specific sectors or industries, such as consumer goods companies or the insurance sector, leading to a lack of comprehensive understanding across various sectors. For instance, Adegrooye et al. (2017) noted the limited empirical exploration of executive compensation in Nigeria, particularly concerning equity compensation schemes and market-based performance measures. Additionally, there is a lack of

consistency in findings across studies regarding the relationship between different types of executive compensation and firm performance, as observed by Mohammed et al. (2022) and Ibeawuchi and Onuora (2021). Furthermore, the literature lacks in-depth analysis of the mechanisms through which executive compensation influences firm performance, particularly in the context of developing economies like Nigeria. The present study contributes to filling these gaps by providing a comprehensive examination of agency compensation and financial performance of quoted manufacturing firms in Nigeria.

METHODOLOGY

The ex post facto design is adopted in this study, as it suits the historical and econometric nature of data and analysis respectively as well as independent manner of collecting and collating utilised data; which enhances validity. Simon & Goes (2013.) argued that ex post facto is ideal when it is impossible and unacceptable to alter the nature of study variables. The duo add that it helps in establishing causal or/and correlational relationship among variables. Therefore, it is relevant for a study of this nature where the strength and direction of link between the exogenous and endogenous variables have not been established. Generally, the population of a research is the collection of the group on which the study’s findings can be generalized. This implies that every conceivable element to which the study’s findings have implication forms the population. Therefore, the population forms the perimeter of elements within which the inference(s) deductable from the study can be applied. This study considers all the 22 quoted consumer goods manufacturing firms in Nigeria. (Nigeria Stock Exchange Reports, 2019)

These data comprise of quantitative expressions of agency cost and performance of quoted consumer goods manufacturing firms in Nigeria. There are several studies performed in the area and the researcher has gathered information from these studies to enhance this research work and to proffer solution to the research problem. Manufacturing firms’ annual statements and reports are deemed to be reliable because they are statutorily required to be audited by a recognized auditing firm before publication.

To test the goodness of fit, the researcher adopted the panel unit root statistics. Often times, the simultaneous use of time series data for a collection of entities leads to multiple heterogeneity given that each time series data could possess heterogenous features. This is often referred to as heterogenous panel which by nature have a preponderance of biases that may culminate in misleading results. It is therefore pertinent to scrutinise the data for the existence of unit root and ensure that the data are stationary at a given level. To introduce panel data unit root tests, consider the autoregressive model:

$$y_{it} = \alpha_i + \gamma_i y_{it-1} + \varepsilon_{it} \tag{3.29}$$

Which we can rewrite as

$$\Delta y_{it} = \alpha_i + \pi_i y_{it-1} + \varepsilon_{it} \tag{3.30}$$

Where $\pi_i = \gamma_i - 1$. The null hypothesis that all series have a unit root then becomes $H_0 : \pi_i = 0$ for all i . a first choice for the alternative hypothesis is that all series are stationary with the same mean-reversion parameter.

Method of Data Analysis

A collection of econometric techniques is used (with the aid of E - Views) to analyse the data. These include panel regression models, cointegration analysis (preceded by unit root test) and granger causality test. Panel data structure allows us to take into account the unobservable and constant heterogeneity, that is, the specific features of each quoted firm.

Panel Regression Technique

The regression technique is often considered as the best linear unbiased estimator due to its predictive precision, besides, it has the advantage of ease in comprehension and application. However, for the panel or pooled regression analysis the choice between the fixed effects and random effects regression has to be determined by the use of the Hausman test. However, irrespective of the model or parameters, the properties of a regression model are given as:

a. Results of Coefficients

Intercept or Constant

The intercept in the equation implies the relative/marginal effect on the explained or exogenous variable when all explanatory or endogenous variables get unchanged or held constant. In other words, it establishes the slope of the regression, which implies the change on the criterion variable when the predictor variables are 0.

Regression Coefficients:

These typify marginal change on the exogenous variable as a consequence of a unit change in an explanatory variable where other explanatory variables are held constant.

Standard Error (of Measurement)

The standard error estimates test the reliability in that, it gives a foresight of the dispersion of the measurement errors in estimation. It is obtained by averaging the standard deviation over all study elements. Reliability is based on the noisiness of the estimates as high output indicates commensurate noise while low result portrays solid level of reliability.

T-Statistic

T – Statistic tests the hypothesis that the estimated parameters considerably differ from zero. Generally, it is derived by the ratio of the coefficient to the standard error of the coefficient. **Decision Rule**

Compare the calculated t-statistics with the tabulated value. If the calculated t-statistics < tabulated t-statistics, reject null hypothesis; else, If calculated t-statistics > tabulated t-statistics, do not reject the null hypothesis.

Probability

Also referred to as p-value provides an easy platform of verifying the rejection or otherwise of given hypotheses. As a rule of thumb, if probability is less than the established significance level, the stated hypothesis should be rejected; otherwise it is not to be rejected.

Summary Statistics

R-Squared (R^2)

Otherwise called the “goodness of fit” value estimates the ratio of variation in the exogenous variable as a consequence of the endogenous variable. Basically used in regression models to rectify homoskedastic errors, it explains variance in association among variables. Where the model fits perfectly, the coefficient of determination is 1, otherwise, the closer the ratio is to one, the better the model it represents.

Adjusted R-Squared

The adjusted R^2 is a better indicator of the model’s “fitness” as it takes into cognizance, the addition of more endogenous variables in the model; this make up for the limitations of the R^2 which basically remains the same despite the addition of more independent variable to the model.

F - Statistic

The F – statistic tests if the aggregation of dependent variables in a given model has significant relationship with the exogenous variable or not.

Decision Rule

Compare the calculated F-statistics with the tabulated value. If the calculated F-statistics < tabulated F-statistics, reject null hypothesis; else, If calculated F-statistics > tabulated F-statistics, do not reject the null hypothesis.

Probability

Also referred to as p-value provides an easy platform of verifying the rejection or otherwise of given hypotheses. As a rule of thumb, if probability is less than the established significance level, the stated hypothesis should be rejected; otherwise it is not to be rejected.

Standard Error of the Regression

The standard error of the regression gives us an indication of how much the point estimate is likely to vary from the corresponding population parameter.

Durbin-Watson Statistic

Data used for analysis could have problems of serial correlation. In order to detect and proffer solution to such anomalies, the Durbin – Watson test is carried out. As established, the DW is between 0 and 4, with a DW of 2 considered to indicate the absence of auto correlation. Although, a DW that hovers around 2 is acceptable, there is evidence of serial correlation if the Durbin–Watson statistic is substantially less than 2. Serial correlation in itself does not hamper the reliability; but it distorts validity. Alternatively, When there is presence of autocorrelation, the First order autoregressive scheme was employed to correct it. The hypotheses states that:

H₀: P = 0 (There is serial independence in the errors)

H₁: P > 0 (There is first order (AR) positive autocorrelation.

When the Durbin Watson Statistic (DW-Stat) is lesser than lower Durbin Watson (D_L), the null hypothesis (H₀) is being rejected if the Durbin Watson statistics is greater than the upper Durbin Watson (D_u), the null (H₀) is then accepted.

Regression Model Specification

Agency compensation

$$ROE = f(ES, EEI, EB, OC) \tag{3.14}$$

$$EPS = f(ES, EEI, EB, OC) \tag{3.15}$$

$$ROE = \alpha_0 + \alpha_1 ES + \alpha_2 EEI + \alpha_3 EB + \alpha_4 OC + \mu \tag{3.20}$$

$$EPS = \alpha_0 + \alpha_1 ES + \alpha_2 EEI + \alpha_3 EB + \alpha_4 OC + \mu \tag{3.21}$$

Where

ROE= Return on equity

EPS= Earnings per share

ES = Executive salaries of the quoted consumer goods manufacturing firms proxy by log of total executive salary

EEI = Executive equity incentives of the quoted consumer goods manufacturing firms proxy by log of executive equity holding

EB = Executive bonuses of the quoted consumer goods manufacturing firms proxy by log of executive bonuses of shares issued

OC = Ownership Concentration of the quoted consumer goods manufacturing firms proxy by log of the 5 largest executive equity investment.

μ = Error Term

$\beta_1 - \beta_4$
 β_0 = Coefficient of Independent Variables to the Dependent Variables
 = Regression Intercept

Hausman Test

The Hausman test is used to establish the appropriate choice between random effect regression and fixed effect regression (Brooks, 2014). Since heterogeneity invalidates the cardinal assumption of homogenous deviation of endogenous variables which underpins the application of random effect model, the test is imperative to decide if a variable can be treated as a distinct element with separate structural equation or as an exogenous variable. Croissant & Millio (2019) succinctly noted that Hausman test detects endogenous regressors in a regression model.

Fixed Effects Model

Fixed effects models are a class of statistical models in which the levels (i.e. values) of endogenous variables are assumed to be constant. That is, over the time frame covered by the data (daily, weekly, monthly etc.) the intercept remains constant, however it varies cross-sectional. Nevertheless, the slopes for all endogenous variables remain constant cross-sectional and over time. Thus:

$$y_{it} = \alpha_j + x_{it}^1 \beta + \varepsilon_{it} \quad \varepsilon_{it} \approx HD(0, \sigma^2) \tag{3.26}$$

Expressing this in a regression framework, we have:

$$y_{it} = \sum_{j=1}^N \alpha_j d_{ij} + x_{ij} \beta + \varepsilon_{it} \quad \varepsilon_{it} \tag{3.27}$$

Where $d_{ij} = 1$ if $i=j$ and 0 elsewhere.

Random Effects Model

The stochastic term, otherwise referred to as white noise or error term is usually added in regression models to account for endogenous variables excluded in the model. These endogenous variables are assumed to be homoscedastic, this often culminates in the assumption that the parameters are distributed identically and independently. Thus we write the random effects model as:

$$Y_{it} = \alpha + \beta x_{it} + \omega_{it}, \quad \omega_{it} = \epsilon_i + v_{it} \tag{3.28}$$

Where x_{it} is still a 1 x k vector of explanatory variables, but unlike the fixed effects model, there are no dummy variables to capture the heterogeneity in the cross-sectional dimension.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

Table 1: Short Run Regression Results on Return on Equity

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
Pooled Effect Model				
OC	-0.152437	0.057176	-2.666079	0.0083
ESS	0.137741	0.108572	1.268662	0.2059
EEI	0.152750	0.143394	1.065243	0.2880
EB	0.262874	0.107986	2.434337	0.0157
C	0.013746	0.814692	0.016873	0.9866
R-squared	0.117197	Mean dependent var		1.243964
Adjusted R-squared	0.100773	S.D. dependent var		1.249766
S.E. of regression	1.185123	Akaike info criterion		3.200036
Sum squared resid	301.9712	Schwarz criterion		3.277164
Log likelihood	-347.0039	Hannan-Quinn criter.		3.231182
F-statistic	7.135600	Durbin-Watson stat		0.841389
Prob(F-statistic)	0.000021			
Fixed Effect Model				
OC	-0.062710	0.109562	-0.572370	0.5677
ESS	0.403035	0.221545	1.819202	0.0704
EEI	-0.114821	0.212279	-0.540898	0.5892
EB	-0.169263	0.244654	-0.691846	0.4899
C	0.710043	1.586512	0.447549	0.6550
Effects Specification				
Cross-section fixed (dummy variables)				
R-squared	0.365051	Mean dependent var		1.243964
Adjusted R-squared	0.283228	S.D. dependent var		1.249766
S.E. of regression	1.058082	Akaike info criterion		3.061387
Sum squared resid	217.1902	Schwarz criterion		3.462452
Log likelihood	-310.7525	Hannan-Quinn criter.		3.223347
F-statistic	4.461461	Durbin-Watson stat		1.094713
Prob(F-statistic)	0.000000			

Random Effect Model				
OC	-0.115558	0.078197	-1.477783	0.0009
ESS	0.227754	0.147122	1.548063	0.0031
EEI	-0.007796	0.173936	-0.044820	0.9643
EB	0.167948	0.152655	1.100179	0.1725
C	0.272767	1.125283	0.242398	0.8087
Effects Specification				
			S.D.	Rho
Cross-section random			0.555085	0.2158
Idiosyncratic random			1.058082	0.7842
Weighted Statistics				
R-squared	0.738507	Mean dependent var		0.642191
Adjusted R-squared	0.520619	S.D. dependent var		1.077311
S.E. of regression	1.066147	Sum squared resid		244.3839
F-statistic	5.152670	Durbin-Watson stat		0.988071
Prob(F-statistic)	0.000042			
Unweighted Statistics				
R-squared	0.099485	Mean dependent var		1.243964
Sum squared resid	308.0298	Durbin-Watson stat		0.833852
Correlated Random Effects - Hausman Test				
Test Summary		Chi-Sq. Statistic	Chi-Sq. d.f.	Prob.
Cross-section random		7.290111	4	0.1213

Source: computed from E-view 9.0

Analysis of Results

Given that the Chi-Sq. Probability is greater than 0.05, being 0.1213, the random effect model is adopted. The table also shows comparable differences between fixed and random effect models in the results, as the results in the table show 0.49, 0.29, 0.391 and 0.0778 for ownership concentration, executive salaries, executive equity incentives and executive bonuses respectively, which is significant. This implies that there is a significant difference between random and fixed effect model. As regards the model summary, the R² in the random effects model is 0.738 implying that agency compensation accounts for approximately 74% variation in return on equity of quoted consumer goods manufacturing companies in Nigeria. The adjusted R² also shows 0.52 implying that irrespective of the number of endogenous variables, agency compensation would not account for more than 52% variation in return on equity of the selected companies. The Durbin Watson is 1.983404 as computed from the random effect results at 5% level of significance with four explanatory variables and 220 observations. This is greater than the calculated DW for dL and du which are 0.861 and 1.562 respectively. Besides, given that it revolves around 2, it is permissible; therefore, there is no evidence of serial correlation.

Furthermore, the movement between the endogenous and exogenous variables as seen from the coefficients shows that the constant of the model is 0.272767, implying that if the endogenous variables are held constant or unchanged, the exogenous variable - return on equity will rise by 0.27 units periodically. The coefficient of the parameters or endogenous variables show that ownership concentration and executive equity incentives have negative relationship with return on equity, while executive salaries and executive bonuses have positive relationship with return on equity of quoted consumer goods manufacturing firms in Nigeria. The magnitude is such that, a unit increase in OC and EEI will result in a 0.115 and 0.007 units fall in return on equity or vice versa, while on the other hand, a unit rise in ES and EB will lead to a 0.0.227 and 0.167 increase in the return on equity of quoted consumer firms in Nigeria.

The severity of relationship shows that ownership concentration and executive salaries have significant relationship with return on equity given that their p-values are less than 0.05, being 0.0009 and 0.0031 respectively; while on the other hand, executive equity incentives and executive bonuses are seen to have insignificant relationship with return on equity of the selected firms as indicated by p-values that are greater than 0.05, which are 0.9643 and 0.1725 respectively. Comprehensively, the probability of the F-

statistics is 0.000042, being less than 0.05; therefore agency compensation has a statistically significant relationship with the return on equity of quoted consumer goods manufacturing firms in Nigeria.

Table 2: Short Run Regression Results on Earnings per Share

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
Pooled Effect Regression Results				
OC	-0.052023	0.036102	-1.440997	0.1510
ESS	-0.122928	0.068550	-1.793257	0.0743
EEI	0.427350	0.090495	4.722337	0.0000
EB	0.177948	0.068178	2.610060	0.0097
C	5.747503	0.514393	11.17336	0.0000
R-squared	0.208510	Mean dependent var		7.061818
Adjusted R-squared	0.193785	S.D. dependent var		0.833369
S.E. of regression	0.748278	Akaike info criterion		2.280379
Sum squared resid	120.3826	Schwarz criterion		2.357507
Log likelihood	-245.8417	Hannan-Quinn criter.		2.311526
F-statistic	14.15991	Durbin-Watson stat		0.481880
Prob(F-statistic)	0.000000			
Fixed Effect Regression Model				
OC	0.047680	0.041045	1.161638	0.2468
ESS	-0.058954	0.082998	-0.710299	0.4784
EEI	0.262663	0.079523	3.302967	0.0011
EB	0.073297	0.091675	0.799535	0.4250
C	5.759127	0.594304	9.690535	0.0000
Effects Specification				
Cross-section fixed (dummy variables)				
R-squared	0.799590	Mean dependent var		7.061818
Adjusted R-squared	0.773764	S.D. dependent var		0.833369
S.E. of regression	0.396385	Akaike info criterion		1.097735
Sum squared resid	30.48155	Schwarz criterion		1.498800
Log likelihood	-94.75084	Hannan-Quinn criter.		1.259696
F-statistic	30.96070	Durbin-Watson stat		1.860824
Prob(F-statistic)	0.000000			
Random Effect Regression Model				
OC	-0.051425	0.036633	-1.403777	0.1619
ESS	-0.122907	0.069608	-1.765692	0.0789
EEI	0.450221	0.094030	4.788038	0.0000
EB	0.182418	0.069606	2.620710	0.0094
C	5.639666	0.531947	10.60194	0.0000
Effects Specification				
Period fixed (dummy variables)				
R-squared	0.224521	Mean dependent var		7.061818
Adjusted R-squared	0.175583	S.D. dependent var		0.833369
S.E. of regression	0.756677	Akaike info criterion		2.341762
Sum squared resid	117.9475	Schwarz criterion		2.557720
Log likelihood	-243.5938	Hannan-Quinn criter.		2.428971
F-statistic	4.587867	Durbin-Watson stat		0.461375
Prob(F-statistic)	0.000001			
Correlated Random Effects - Hausman Test				
Test Summary		Chi-Sq. Statistic	Chi-Sq. d.f.	Prob.
Cross-section random	2.599490	4	0.6269	

Source: computed from E-view 9.0

Analysis of Results

It is established from the Chi-Sq. Probability, which is greater than 0.05, (being 0.6269), that the random effect model is adopted. The table also shows comparable differences between fixed and random effect models in the results, as the results in the table show 0.34, 0.88, 0.57 and 0.58 for ownership concentration, executive salaries, executive equity incentives and executive bonuses respectively, which

is significant. This implies that there is a significant difference between random and fixed effect model. As regards the model summary, the R^2 in the random effects model is 0.824521 implying that agency compensation accounts for approximately 82% variation in earnings per share of quoted consumer goods manufacturing firms in Nigeria. The adjusted R^2 also shows 0.676 implying that irrespective of the number of endogenous variables, agency compensation would not account for more than 68% variation in earnings per share of the selected companies. The Durbin Watson is 1.86 as computed from the random effect results at 5% level of significance with four explanatory variables and 220 observations. This is greater than the calculated DW for dL and du which are 0.861 and 1.562 respectively. Besides, given that it revolves around 2, it is permissible; therefore, there is no evidence of serial correlation.

Furthermore, the movement between the endogenous and exogenous variables as seen from the coefficients shows that the constant of the model is 0.272767, implying that if the endogenous variables are held constant or unchanged, the exogenous variable - earnings per share will rise by 0.27 units periodically. The coefficient of the parameters or endogenous variables show that ownership concentration and executive equity incentives have negative relationship with earnings per share, while executive salaries and executive bonuses have positive relationship with earnings per share of quoted consumer goods manufacturing firms in Nigeria. The magnitude is such that, a unit increase in OC and EEI will result in a 0.115 and 0.007 units fall in earnings per share or vice versa, while on the other hand, a unit rise in ES and EB will lead to a 0.0.227 and 0.167 increase in the earnings per share of quoted consumer firms in Nigeria. The severity of relationship shows that executive equity incentives and executive bonuses have significant relationship with earnings per share given that their p-values are less than 0.05, being 0.000 and 0.0094 respectively; while on the other hand, ownership concentration and executive salaries are seen to have insignificant relationship with earnings per share of the selected firms as indicated by p-values that are greater than 0.05, which are 0.16169 and 0.0789 respectively. Comprehensively, the probability of the F-statistics is 0.000001, being less than 0.05; therefore agency compensation has a statistically significant relationship with the earnings per share of quoted consumer goods manufacturing firms in Nigeria.

CONCLUSION

This study examined the relationship between agency compensation and financial performance of quoted manufacturing firms. Model one found that agency compensation accounts for approximately 74% variation in return on equity of quoted consumer goods manufacturing companies in Nigeria. The magnitude is such that, a unit increase in OC and EEI will result in a 0.115 and 0.007 units fall in return on equity or vice versa, while on the other hand, a unit rise in ES and EB will led to a 0.0.227 and 0.167 increase in the return on equity of quoted consumer firms in Nigeria. Model two found that agency compensation accounts for approximately 82% variation in earnings per share of quoted consumer goods manufacturing firms in Nigeria. . The coefficient of the parameters or endogenous variables show that ownership concentration and executive equity incentives have negative relationship with earnings per share, while executive salaries and executive bonuses have positive relationship with earnings per share of quoted consumer goods manufacturing firms in Nigeria. The magnitude is such that, a unit increase in OC and EEI will result in a 0.115 and 0.007 units fall in earnings per share or vice versa, while on the other hand, a unit rise in ES and EB will lead to a 0.0.227 and 0.167 increase in the earnings per share of quoted consumer firms in Nigeria. From the above, the study conclude that agency compensation determine the financial performance of the quoted firms.

RECOMMENDATIONS

- i. The manufacturing firms should consider establishment policies for executive stockholding. This will enhance management in planning and managing forts that affect corporate valuation and management of the quoted manufacturing firms should adopt good compensation structure, welfare, and incentive packages as these would positively motivate executives and consequently improve corporate valuation.

- ii. Policy makers need to provide adequate regulation on the determination of equity incentive of the directors of listed companies, this will reduce the agency cost that negatively effect of corporate valuation and the over bearing influence of directors in annual general meetings.
- iii. Management should review salary structures to ensure competitiveness and alignment with employee responsibilities and performance, potentially leading to increased productivity and profitability. Management should implement performance-based bonus schemes tied to specific key performance indicators or financial targets to incentivize employees towards strategic goals and drive productivity.

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